
An Empirical study on innovations and its impact on purchase intention of residential real estate projects**Dr.Hemanthkumar.S.&Nishanth.A.Patil****Associate Professor, M P Birla Institute of Management, Bangalore ,India,
Assistant Manager, Total Environment Building Systems Private Limited,****ABSTRACT**

In the current scenario the competition in the real estate is fast growing. Sensing the increasing competition and demand for residential houses wealthy individuals and corporate take the role of avatar of residential real estates and bring the residential real estate industry to an unprecedented level with the help of innovation to increase their operating effectiveness and profitability. Innovation in residential projects will drive the perception of customers in a complete departure from the traditional industry experience and the make the whole experience of purchasing innovative residential real estate projects as warm and personal. The scope of the research is important considering the changing environment which poses a challenge for the real estate companies to evolve continuously. This research will help us to find the impact of innovation on purchase intension of consumers and it will also help us in analyzing the relationship between the dimensions of innovation and the influence of demographic factors on the purchase intensions of customers. The study will provide relevant recommendations for the real estate developers to be different from competitors for creation of value for money concept to the customers.

Keywords: Customers, Demographic, Innovation, Real Estate, Perception

I .Introduction

Demographic statistics and various studies suggest that India can be a land of opportunities and globally can be a leading destination for real estate business. The urban population of India is equivalent to the total population of the United States of America and United Kingdom, and about 10 million people are migrating into cities from the rural area. The migration has resulted to account for 18.8 million housing shortages approximately in the urban area. In present scenario the overall development of India's core infrastructure has been contributed by the real estate and construction sectors of India. The growth of real estate industry is linked to developments of various allied sectors like entertainment(hotels, resorts, cinema theatres) industries, retail industry, hospitality industry, IT industry (like call centers) and economic services (hospitals, schools) and etc and vice versa. Over the years Indian real estate industry witnessed substantially low levels of expertise / financial resources because the sector has been traditionally technology (IT) - dominated by a number of small regional players existing in the local market. Historically, the sector has accounted for low levels of transparency because it has high net worth individuals traditionally tapped in its basket apart from other informal sources of financing but, the sector has not been benefited from the various institutional capital existing in the market. Due to the sector's growth, and the present dynamics of real estate industry which reflects the changing consumer's expectations of higher quality the above stated scenario has surpassed a change due to integration of India with the global economy. The proposed amendments in the real estate laws have gripped the Indian real estate sector with changing economic scenario resulting in a state of flux. This change has been embraced by both buyers and developers in this evolving environment. Real estate developers are coming up with concept of innovative projects and new formats of properties to enhance their presence in this changing environment. Economic growth results in demand for real estate growth due to landscaping opportunities persisting in the sector. Rising purchasing power of individuals has led to buying of new homes, offices and shops resulting in overall growth of real estate sector. The real estate industry is making crunching efforts continuously considering the dimensions of innovation and trying to evolve constantly to remain on acme and generating a podium for the buyers to meet their demand in this evolving economic scenario.

1.1 Current Scenario of the Real Estate Market in India

Business land segment is in blast in India. In the most recent fifteen years, post liberalization of the economy, Indian land business has taken an upturn and is relied upon to develop from the current USD 14 billion to a USD 102 billion in the following 10 years. This development can be credited to ideal demographics, expanding buying power, existence of customer, friendly banks & housing finance companies, demonstrable skill in land and positive changes started by the legislature to pull in worldwide financial specialists.

1.2 Characteristics of the Real Estate Market in India

The property market in India has generally been disorderly and divided. Be that as it may, the later past has seen a union of positions in the business sector as designers is extending their abilities to the most extreme so as to take care of the developing business sector demand, which thusly has supported expansive undertakings with sourced financing. The IPOs by expansive land designers like Sobha, Raheja and DLF have prompted association of the business sector in the Tier I urban communities, however the Tier II and Tier III urban areas still show the attributes of a sloppy business sector. Whilst the Indian land advertise still needs straightforwardness and liquidity contrasted with more develop land showcases, the expanding necessities of multinational occupiers, and in addition the flood of universal property consultancies has prompted the presentation of more noteworthy accessibility of business sector data, both in distributed and private structure pushing the area to a composed business sector structure.

1.3 Innovation

The procedure of interpreting a thought or innovation into a decent or administration that makes esteem or for which clients will pay.

To be called advancement, a thought must be replicable at an efficient cost and should fulfill a particular need. Development includes planned utilization of data, creative energy and activity in inferring more prominent or distinctive qualities from assets, and incorporates all procedures by which new thoughts are produced and changed over into valuable items. In business, development regularly comes about when thoughts are connected by the organization so as to further fulfill the requirements and desires of the clients.

1.4 Dimensions of Innovation

Figure1.10.1: Showing Dimensions of Innovation

- **Product innovation** (first P of the 4Ps) is the easiest to understand. It means changes in the things which an organization offers.
- **Process innovation** (second P of 4Ps) is also quite easy to understand. It means changes in the organization's processes. In the other words it means changes in the ways in which organization is created and delivered.
- **Position innovation** (third P of 4Ps) to understand needs some thinking and it is not as clear as the first two innovation types. It means changes in the context in which the products/services are introduced.
- **Paradigm innovation**, it is by far the hardest to understand. Meaning for that are changes in the underlying mental models which frame what the organization does.

II. Literature Review

Mohamad Idham Md Razak, et.al (2013) this study talked about buy goal of purchasers considering the late advancement in land division. The idea of land was disclosed alluding to things that are immovable, for example, area and changes forever joined to the area for instance house or whatever other building. Aside from the customary variables the development of land division is controlled by different other united elements. The study helped in comprehension and anticipating the acquiring aim of purchasers towards property, particularly occupants in Setia Alam by embracing the model from Gibler K.M. what's more, Nelson S.L. (1998) which gave an understanding on all the components thought about for the development of the land segment. The exploration demonstrated that their exists huge relationship between all the components that speak to the precursors for the elements that impact acquiring goal towards property in Setia Alam and free variables, for example, identity, information, social class and reference amass that impact the obtaining expectation towards property in Setia Alam.

Dr. A. Mohamed Sali, et.al (2013) this study broke down the significant determinants impacting the purchaser conduct towards buy of private pads. Because of rising salary level and changing ways of life lodging industry in India has seen gigantic development in the course of recent years bringing about changing rustic lodging scene. Passage of corporate houses like DLF, Parsvnath, Omaxe and simple money alternatives from monetary organizations and government support has given another measurement to the land business in India with development of loft promoters who build condo and offer them. The property purchasers are hoping to abuse the best deal in the business sector with numerous lodging fund alternatives accessible from different loaning offices and financing costs running at unsurpassed low. The comprehension of the purchaser conduct towards buy of private pads is possibly a noteworthy source giving aggressive edge to promoters which has opened the conduits all through the nation and world because of spread of loft society giving tremendous open door for the exploration to fill the learning hole of the individuals who get occupied with lodging market exercises, for example, designers, financial specialists, purchasers and venders.

Dr. Mostafa Kamal & Shah Alam Kabir Pramanik (2015) in this study clarified clients purchasing state of mind, purchasing expectation and conduct considering different models and hypotheses that have been proposed. The hypothesis of arranged conduct was connected to clarify purchasing aim in setting of Real Estate particularly on loft purchasing conduct which gave another way to deal with this examination. An organized survey was utilized to gather the information from 275 respondents and examination of information was made utilizing SPSS. The forerunners of clients purchasing state of mind were investigated considering the six variables in particular venture offices, natural issues, area and correspondence, physical quality, advancement and costs that affect clients purchasing disposition and purchasing goal. The examination utilized Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test both the proposed demonstrate and estimated connections among the develops. The discoveries of this study demonstrated that purchasing aim is firmly impacted by purchasing state of mind of the clients. Along these lines the discoveries of the article will be useful to Real Estate engineers, advertisers, and strategy creators to better comprehend, portion and fulfill the clients. This article shows that client based brand value and client faithfulness especially in Real Estate (Apartment Market) will increase upper hands and in addition accomplish maintainable advancement of the area.

Dr.P.B.Sakthivel & M.F. Nazeer Ahamed (2013) in this study clarified home-purchaser's inclinations of person which may fluctuate starting with one individual then onto the next. The primary goal of this article is to make mindfulness among the manufacturers about what home purchasers incline toward as far as both administration measurement and item amid the development or buy of their private houses by deciding the house purchaser's inclinations and private fulfillment of clients. A hypothetical model was created connecting home-purchaser's inclinations and consumer loyalty considering the reactions from center meeting led among the respondents who are chiefly home-purchasers of Chennai City in India to make sense of the Voice of the Customer (Feedback) on their inclinations on purchasing a house. Keeping in mind the end goal to comprehend the inclinations of the home-purchasing clients and eventually in accomplishing consumer loyalty the created model connecting home-purchaser's inclinations and consumer loyalty will positively be useful to the development business.

III .Research Methodology

3.1 Statement of Problem:

In the current scenario the competition in the real estate is fast growing. Sensing the increasing competition and demand for residential houses wealthy individuals and corporate take the role of avatar of residential real estates and bring the residential real estate industry to an unprecedented level with the help of innovation to increase their operating effectiveness and profitability. Innovation in residential projects will drive the perception of customers in a complete departure from the traditional industry experience and the make the whole experience of purchasing innovative residential real estate projects as warm and personal.

3.2 Research Objectives:

1. To analyze the impact of innovation on purchase intention of residential real estate projects.
2. To explore the impact of innovation on demographic factors of consumers.
3. To analyze the relationship between consumers buying attitude and buying intention.
4. To analyze significant relationship between dimensions of innovation and demographic factors of consumers.

3.3 Hypothesis:

- **H₀:** There is no significant difference between demographic factors such as age, gender, and education background on dimensions of innovation influencing purchase decision of residential real estate projects.
- **H_a:** There is a significant difference between demographic factors such as age, gender, and education background on dimensions of innovation influencing purchase decision of residential real estate projects.

3.4 Primary Data:

Primary data has been collected using a structured and focused questionnaire; which covered various dimensions of the research questions. Convenient sampling technique was used to collect data for the research. The sample size consisted of 100 respondents who are frequently involved in investments of residential real estate projects.

3.5 Secondary Data:

Secondary data has been collected from books, internet, literature and other relevant documents. Magazines, Journals, Fact sheets and Web resources, online libraries and websites are other sources.

3.6 Statistical Techniques used

Anova:

The application of ANOVA test in this study was to determine whether there is a significant difference between the expected frequencies and the observed frequencies in one or more categories. The test was also used to find out whether there is an overall significance between demographic factors on dimensions of innovation influencing purchase intention of residential real estate projects.

IV .Data Analysis**4.1 Testing of hypothesis:****Table 1:** Showing the Testing of Hypothesis for various dimensions of innovation.

Hypothesis	Level Of Significance	F- Value	P- Value	Accepted/Rejected
There is no significant difference in mean score of paradigm dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.	5%	3.920	.011	Alternative hypothesis is accepted.
There is no significant difference in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.	5%	1.787	.115	Null hypothesis is accepted.
There is no significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.	5%	2.634	.025	Alternative hypothesis is accepted.
There is no significant difference in mean score of process dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across gender.	5%	.289	.592	Null hypothesis is accepted.
There is no significant		2.664	.046	

difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across gender.	5%			Alternative hypothesis is accepted	
There is no significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across Education Background.	5%		.933	.208	Null hypothesis is accepted
There is no significant difference in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across marital status.	5%		2.399	.025	Alternative hypothesis is accepted

4.2 Interpretation:

1. H_0 : There is no significant difference in mean score of paradigm dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.

H_a : There is a significant difference in mean score of paradigm dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is an overall significance in mean score of paradigm dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=3.920$, $p=0.011$, $p<0.05$) across age groups. Since the p-value is less than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative is accepted. In other words, we can conclude that the paradigm dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision varies across different age groups.

2. H_0 : There is no significant difference in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.

H_a: There is a significant difference in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is no overall significance in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=1.787$, $p=0.115$, $p>0.05$) across age groups. Since the p-value is greater than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. In other words, we can conclude that the product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision remain same across different age groups.

3. H₀: There is no significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.

H_a: There is a significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across different age groups.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is an overall significance in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=2.634$, $p=0.025$, $p<0.05$) across age groups. Since the p-value is less than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative is accepted. In other words, we can conclude that the position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision varies across different age groups.

4. H₀: There is no significant difference in mean score of process dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across gender.

H_a: There is a significant difference in mean score of process dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across gender.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is no overall significance in mean score of process dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=0.289$, $p=0.592$, $p>0.05$) across gender. Since the p-value is greater than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. In other words, we can conclude that that the process dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision remain same across different gender.

5. H₀: There is no significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across gender.

H_a: There is a significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across gender.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is an overall significance in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=2.664$, $p=0.046$, $p<0.05$) across age groups. Since the p-value is less than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative is accepted. In other words, we can conclude that the position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision varies across different gender.

6. H₀: There is no significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across Education Background.

H_a: There is a significant difference in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across Education Background.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is no overall significance in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=0.933$, $p=0.208$, $p>0.05$) across education background. Since the p-value is greater than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. In other words, we can conclude that the position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision remain same across different education background.

7. H_0 : There is no significant difference in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across marital status.

H_a : There is a significant difference in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across marital status.

Inference:

The One Way ANOVA result from the Table shows that there is an overall significance in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision ($F=2.399$, $p=0.025$, $p<0.05$) across marital status. Since the p-value is less than 5 % level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative is accepted. In other words, we can conclude that the product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision varies across marital status.

V. Findings

- The majority of the respondents are from the group of 30-40 years and very few falls under the category of age group 20-30.
- The majority of the respondents are male and the remaining of them are female.
- The majorities (constituting 56% of the sample) of the respondents are married and the remaining 44% are unmarried.
- From this study we can observe that majority of the respondents are undergraduates and respondents coming from education background of postgraduate and pre-university constitute 24% of the sample. The remaining fall under the category of higher secondary.
- The majority of the respondent's income level is from 10 lakh to 15 lakh and very few falls under the income level of 15 lakh to 20 lakh.
- The majority of the respondents have purchased residential real estate projects and the remaining hasn't purchased residential real estate projects.
- We can observe that the satisfaction level of the majority of respondents was neutral with respect to a criterion that the purchase of previous house was a good buy.
- The majority of the respondents belong to family size of 3 and the remaining respondents belong to family size of 1.
- It was found that there is an overall significance in mean score of position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across age groups. In other words, we can conclude that the position dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision varies across different age groups.
- It was evident from anova there is an overall significance in mean score of product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision across marital status. In other words, we can conclude that the product dimension of innovation influencing purchase decision varies across marital status.
- It was found that there is an overall significance in mean score of investments in projects considering the aspects of Innovative dimensions across education background. In other words, we can conclude that the investments in projects considering the aspects of Innovative dimensions vary across different education background.

VI .Suggestions

Due to the booming real estate industry advertising plays a vital role in attracting customers. . Investigation of customers buying conduct is crucially imperative for settling on educated and exploratory choices. Since the customers' choice to buy or get rid of items is in light of their apparent nature of the items being offered, designers need to convey items complying with the pertinent quality properties furthermore having the ability to fulfill their necessities. The designers need to consider such imperative variables which are independent and their particular contributing traits in planning and promoting of private land.

Marketers need to apply the suggestions based on findings of this study while making their major policy decisions on design, construction and marketing of residential houses.

- Real Estate Developers need to come up with new formats of properties to capitalize on the changing environment. They should evolve marketing patterns to remain on top of the situation and to generate demand from buyers.
- The residential real estate companies should bring in innovation considering the different dimensions of innovations influencing purchase decision of customers during design, Construction and marketing of residential houses.
- This approach will help the property investors to improve the products and services. They should also have improvement in their marketing strategy to be different from competitors for creation of value for money concept to the consumers.
- Make great brand attention to pull in new buyers and keep steadfast clients even it can influence expectation to purchase at the low level yet it can help for memory creation. The great brand mindfulness technique, for example, enhancing social obligation programs, giving different great quality will increase the overall operating effectiveness and profitability of the residential real estate industry taking it to an unprecedented level with the help of innovation.

VII .Conclusion

In the current scenario due to fast changing environment demand for residential houses has reached unprecedented level. The reason for this might be the change in consumption pattern and income level of the buyers resulting in huge migration of rural population to urban area. The real estate industry is fast evolving in order to generate demand from buyers. However, lack of sufficient research in India on this account, encouraged this research. The purpose of this study was to advance the understanding about the impact of demographic factors on dimensions of innovation influencing purchase intention of residential real estate projects.

It is evident from the study that dimensions of innovation have a significant impact on the purchase decision of buyers. Hence there are huge opportunities for the residential real estate companies to bring in innovation in the competitive market to drive the perception and purchase intention of consumers. Residential real estate companies take the role of avatar in design, construction and marketing of residential houses to be different from competitors for creation of value for money concept to the customers. Demand for residential houses in context with dimensions of innovation will increase the overall operating effectiveness and profitability of the residential real estate industry.

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